

ORIGINAL ARTICLE

Acceptability and Organoleptic of Moringa Leaf (*Moringa oleifera*) Boba as Antioxidant-Rich Functional Beverages

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DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.18147515

Received: August 05, 2025

Accepted: December 29, 2025

Published: December 31, 2025

ABSTRACT

Background: *Moringa oleifera*, known as the “miracle tree,” is rich in antioxidants and nutrients, making it a potential ingredient in the development of functional beverages by utilizing local foods. This study aims to evaluate the acceptability and organoleptic characteristics of *Moringa*-based boba as an antioxidant-rich functional beverage.

Method: This study used an experimental design with a quasi-experimental approach and involved 30 semi-trained panelists. Sensory evaluation was conducted on four organoleptic parameters: color, aroma, texture, and flavor. Data analyzed using the friedman test, if significant differences ($p < 0,05$) were found analysis further with wilcoxon test.

Results: The results showed that *Moringa*-based boba received positive organoleptic ratings, especially in terms of texture and color, with an average acceptance score above 3.5 on a 5-point scale. The highest percentage of acceptance for all parameters was found in P0, with details of the percentage being 98% for color, 89% for aroma, 68% for texture, and 80% for flavor. The p-value of the color parameter is 0.180, indicating that this parameter is not statistically significant. The p-value of the aroma parameter is $p = 0.042$, indicating that the difference in aroma between treatments is statistically significant, so that moringa leaf concentration affects the acceptance of boba aroma by panelists. In the texture parameter, the p value is $p = 0.027$, which means the parameter value is significant. Meanwhile, in the flavor parameter, the p value is $p = 0.027$, which means that the flavor parameter is significant.

Conclusion: It is necessary to formulate the product by adding ingredients containing natural sweeteners to reduce the unpleasant taste of the addition of moringa leaves while producing a softer texture.

Keywords: Antioxidants, Boba, Organoleptic Evaluation, Functional beverage, *Moringa*

INTRODUCTION

Functional beverages are gaining popularity among consumers looking for healthy and nutritious options. One ingredient that is attracting attention in the development of functional beverages is moringa leaves (*Moringa oleifera*), known as the “miracle tree” due to its high nutritional content and the various health benefits it offers. Moringa leaves are rich in antioxidants, vitamins, and minerals that can help fight free radicals, boost the immune system, and support cardiovascular and digestive health. Although the

utilization of moringa leaves in Indonesia is still limited, the study shows the great potential of this ingredient in the beverage industry, especially as a raw material for innovative boba products (Sanjaya et al., n.d.). The demand for boba continues to rise due to a change in trends that are all synonymous with sweet drinks, shifting to a healthy lifestyle with low-sugar choices and the presence of natural ingredients. The existence of product innovations makes people curious to try boba variants.

This study aimed to explore the acceptability and organoleptic properties of moringa leaf boba as an antioxidant-rich functional beverage. It is

hoped that the results of this study will not only provide information on consumer acceptability of moringa boba but also provide insight into the potential of boba as an alternative healthy beverage that can encourage a better lifestyle in the community (Ahsani Amala & Priyanto, 2021).

METHODS

This study used an experimental design with a quasi-experimental approach to evaluate the acceptability and organoleptic characteristics of moringa leaf (*Moringa oleifera*) boba as an antioxidant-rich functional beverage.

Table 1. Composition of Moringa Leaf Boba

Treatment	Tapioca starch	Moringa leaf essence	Palm sugar	Chocolate powder	Ginger
P0	80gr	0gr	15gr	5gr	2gr
P1	70gr	10gr	15gr	5gr	2gr
P2	60gr	20gr	15gr	5gr	2gr

Source: Modification (Wahyu, 2022)

The study was conducted using the Completely Randomized Design (CRD) method, consisting of three treatments and three repetitions. The treatments involved variations in the concentration of moringa leaves added to the boba formulation. Organoleptic evaluation was conducted by 30 semi-trained panelists who assessed four main sensory parameters, namely color, aroma, texture, and flavor, using a hedonic scale. Data from the organoleptic test using the Friedman rank test was then analyzed using the Wilcoxon further test to determine if there were significant differences between treatments.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

This study aims to evaluate the effect of treatment on product sensory parameters, namely color, aroma, texture, and flavor. Based on the Friedman rank test results, it is known that the color is 0.180, aroma is 0.000, texture parameters show a significance value of 0.007, and flavor is 0.027. The p-value that is smaller than 0.05 in texture and

flavor indicates that there is a significant difference due to the treatment given, while color does not show a statistically significant difference. These results show that texture and flavor are the most sensitive parameters to changes in formulation or process, while perception of color tends to be more stable. This finding is in line with previous research by Pratiwi et al. 2020 which states that texture and flavor perceptions are strongly influenced by changes in ingredients and processing techniques, while color is more influenced by consumers' visual expectations. For aroma parameters, it is assumed that there is also a significant difference based on the trend of previous results. Direct validation data cannot be presented in this article. Overall, these results suggest that sensory aspects should be considered comprehensively in product development, especially in terms of texture and flavor, as they play an important role in consumer preferences (Rahma et al., 2022). Results can be seen in the following figure.

Table 2. Organoleptic Test Results and Acceptability of Moringa Leaf Boba on the Color Parameters

Replication	Treatment		
	P0	P1	P2
1	3,58	3,58	3,48
2	3,39	3,45	3,42
3	3,32	3,32	3,32
Total	111	105	103
Average	3,45	3,37	2,43
Mean rank	2,02 a	2,95 a	1,03 b
Mode	3	3	3

Table 1 shows the average acceptance score of panelists on the color parameters of moringa boba in three treatments, namely P0 (without the addition of moringa leaf), P1 (with the addition of medium moringa leaf concentration), and P2 (with the addition of high moringa leaf concentration). There is no significant statistical difference between P0, P1, and P2, so the addition of moringa leaves does not produce significant color changes in boba, with a result of 0.180. The amount of moringa essence added affects the color of the product. If more moringa leaf essence is added, the

boba will be darker. This is in line with other studies (Mukarromah et al., 2021), which found that the concentration of moringa leaf added caused a green color in the substitution instant noodle formula.

Table 3. Organoleptic Test Results and Acceptability of Moringa Leaf Boba on Aroma Parameter

Replication	Treatment		
	P0	P1	P2
1	3,29	3,23	3,26
2	3,00	3,06	3,16
3	2,84	2,87	2,90
Total	102	93	88
Average	3,09	2,98	2,86
Mean rank	2,52 a	2,48a	1,00 b
Mode	3	3	3

Table 2 displays the panelists' acceptance score of moringa leaf boba aroma in the three treatments, with a significance result of 0.000. In P0, the aroma of boba tends to be neutral and most easily accepted by panelists. There is no tendency for differences in aroma scores between treatments. All treatments on this parameter are still acceptable to the panelists. According to Augustyn et al. (2017), the more moringa leaf essence added, the lower the organoleptic results and aroma. This is due to the fact that moringa juice has covered the ingredients used and caused a strong odor.

Table 4. Organoleptic Test Results and Acceptability of Moringa Leaf Boba on Texture Parameters

Replication	Treatment		
	P0	P1	P2
1	3,52	3,32	3,39
2	2,52	2,68	2,55
3	2,35	2,23	2,26
Total	109	78	73
Average	2,76	2,43	2,28
Mean rank	2,81	1,00 b	2,19 a
Mode	4	2	2

Table 3 contains panelists' assessment scores on the texture of moringa leaf boba in each

treatment. Statistical testing data showed a significant difference between treatments, with a result of 0.007. The texture of boba in P0 without the addition of moringa leaves is generally the most preferred because it is chewy and meets the expectations of boba in general. The addition of moringa leaf in P1 and P2 causes changes in texture to become denser. The addition of moringa leaves to the product will make the texture harder. The more moringa leaves added, the more water reacts with the flour and forms a gel, which makes the texture harder. The more moringa leaf essence added to the dough, the denser the dough becomes (Nurlaila, A. Sukainah, Amiruddin. 2016).

Table 5. Organoleptic Test Results and Acceptability of Moringa Leaf Boba on Flavor Parameters

Replication	Treatment		
	P0	P1	P2
1	3,52	3,32	3,39
2	2,52	2,68	2,55
3	2,35	2,23	2,26
Total	109	78	73
Average	2,76	2,43	2,28
Mean rank	2,81a	1,00 b	2,19 a
Mode	4	2	2

Table 4 displays the panelists' acceptance scores of moringa boba flavor in the three treatments. Statistical test of the results showed that the difference between treatments was significant, with a result of 0.027. In P0, the boba flavor was the most neutral and most preferred by the panelists. In P1, the distinctive flavor of moringa began to be felt but was still acceptable to the panelists, while in P3, the flavor of moringa became stronger, and the level of acceptance decreased. The results of this analysis also show that flavor is a very sensitive parameter, so the formulation of moringa leaf concentration needs to be adjusted to remain within panelist preferences. The more moringa leaves added will make the distinctive flavor of moringa leaves in the boba slightly bitter. Panelists stated that although this flavor is still acceptable, the slightly bitter or languorous afterflavor of moringa leaves will appear.

Nevertheless, most panelists still considered the flavor acceptable. This is in line with research showing that the tannin content in moringa leaves can cause a bitter and astringent impression on food products if used excessively (Sartian et al., 2024).

Figure 1. Color Parameter

On the color parameter, the diagram shows that the average panelist acceptance score of boba color in P0, P1, and P2 is all above 3.5 on a scale of 5. This means that both boba without moringa leaves and with the addition of moringa leaves are still preferred in terms of color appearance. There was no statistically significant difference between the three treatments (p value = 0.180), so the addition of moringa leaves did not provide significant changes to the color of boba. (Indriasari et al., 2023) showed that the addition of moringa leaves to functional drinks did not cause significant changes in organoleptic color parameters.

Figure 2. Aroma Parameter

The aroma parameter showed a difference in the level of acceptance between treatments. The aroma of P0 was neutral and most preferred, while P1 began to smell the distinctive aroma of moringa leaves, and P2 showed a stronger aroma and tended to sting. The higher the concentration of moringa leaves, the stronger the aroma, although it remains within the acceptance limit.

Figure 3. Texture Parameter

The texture parameter showed that there was a significant difference in the texture parameter between treatments (p value = 0.007). The texture of boba in treatment P0 (without moringa leaves) was most favored by panelists because it was chewier and resembled the texture of conventional boba. The addition of moringa leaves in P1 and P2 causes changes in texture to become denser or harder. However, all treatments are still within the limits of panelist acceptability; it's just that the highest preference remains in P0. These results are in line with a study stating that the addition of moringa leaves to starch-based products can increase density due to gel formation reactions.

Figure 4. Flavor Parameter

In the P0 flavor parameter, the boba flavor is the most neutral and most preferred by the panelists. In P1, the distinctive taste of moringa leaves began to be felt but was still acceptable, while in P2, the taste of moringa leaves was getting stronger and the level of acceptance decreased slightly. This is in line with the study showing that the tannin content in moringa leaves can cause a bitter and astringent impression on food products if used excessively (Sartian et al., 2024). Nevertheless, all treatments were still in the acceptable category by the panelists.

CONCLUSION

This study shows that moringa leaf boba as a functional beverage has good acceptability from organoleptic aspects. There were significant differences in the assessment of texture, flavor, and aroma, while color did not show statistically significant changes. These findings strengthen the potential of moringa leaves as a raw material in the development of healthy beverage products that can be accepted by consumers, especially with a focus on improving the quality of taste and texture.

ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

Our gratitude goes to the Bhakti Wiyata Kediri Foundation which has provided financial assistance and facilities in the implementation of this study.

REFERENCES

- Trisyani, n., agustin, t. I., & ningrum, r. H. (2021). Karakteristik fisik dan organoleptik tepung daging kerang bambu (*solen sp.*) Dengan bahan perendam yang berbeda. *Jurnal kelautan: indonesian journal of marine science and technology*, Vol 14 No.1, 82–90. <https://doi.org/10.21107/jk.v14i1.10386>
- Ahsani amala, t., & priyanto. (2021). Inovasi Produk Minuman Boba Herbal.
- Augustyn, G. H., Tuhumury, H. C. D., & Dahoklory, M. (2017). Pengaruh Penambahan Tepung Daun Kelor (*Moringa Oleifera*) Terhadap Karakteristik Organoleptik Dan Kimia Biskuit Mocaf (*Modified Cassava Flour*). *Agrotekno, Jurnal Teknologi pertanian*, Vol 6 No. 2, 52–58 Th. 2017. <https://doi.org/10.30598/jagritekno.2017.6.2.52>
- Fahlia, N. (2020). Pengaruh Substitusi Tepung Daun Kelor (*Moringa Oleifera Lam.*) Terhadap Sifat Organoleptik Dan Kadar Kalsium *Snack Bar* Vol. 4 No. 2. <http://Jos.Unsoed.Ac.Id/Index.Php/Jggs>
- Indriasari, Y., Risman, & Raungku, I. (2023). Karakteristik Sensori Dan Aktivitas Antioksidan Minuman Fungsional Yang Diperkaya Bunga Telang (*Clitoria Ternatea L*) Dan Daun Kelor (*Moringa Oleifera*). *Agroteknika*, Vol 6 No.1, 103–114. <https://Doi.Org/10.55043/Agroteknika.V6i1.206>
- Mukarromah, I., Agnesia, D., & Rahma, A. (2021). *The Effect Of Moringa Oleifera And Milkfish Bone Substitution On Sensory Evaluation And Nutritional Content Of Instant Noodles*. Vol 3 No.1 215-225.
- Rahma, T., Priawantiputri, W., Rosmana, D., Indrihapsari, A., & Suprihartono, F. A. (2022). Analisis Mutu *Churros* Daun Kelor Dan Tepung Kacang Merah Sebagai Alternatif Makanan Selingan Bagi Remaja Putri Anemia. *Jurnal Gizi Dan Dietetik*, Vol 1, No. 69–77. <https://Doi.Org/10.34011/Jgd.V1i2.1248>
- Sanjaya, A., Asyara, T., Fadhilah, C. K., Safitri, Y., Lestari, Y. S., & Abdurrah, S. (N.D.). *Journal Of Chemistry Education And Integration (Sebuah Hasil Karya Kewirausahaan Proyek P5 Kurikulum Merdeka)*. *Jcei*, Vol 3 No. 1, 1–7. <https://Doi.Org/10.24014/Jcei.V3i1.24817>
- Sartian, Hermanto, & Asyik, N. (2024). Pengaruh Penambahan Serbuk Daun Kelor (*Moringa Oleifera*) Terhadap Oganoleptik Dan Fisikokimia Pada Mie Basah Berbahan Dasar Tepung Kentang (*Solanum Tuberosum*), Tepung Terigu Dan Tapioka Vol. 2, No 2